

INTERNAL STRESS AND DAMAGE ASSESSMENT IN THICK EPOXY BY LASER INDUCED SHOCK WAVE: EFFECTS OF THE PLASTICITY

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ABSTRACT

High performance epoxies are more and more used for structural design in naval and offshore applications. A trend for thick carbon fibre reinforced plastics application appears recently for severely loaded structures, especially for deep water oil extraction. On the other hand it is well known today that internal residual stresses appear during the curing of thermosetting materials, as shown by defects like long fibre wavinesses, cracks and bubbles within the epoxy matrix, especially with increased thickness. The understanding of the undergoing phenomena during the curing of thick epoxy was described in a previous work by a FEM modelling of the thermal, chemical and mechanical couplings [1]. However, to enable a better quality control, pulsed lasers have recently been used in non destructive inspection and characterization of composites [2]. Nevertheless, to assess the experimental set-up of the laser induced shock wave technique, a description of material parameters is required. Because of the complexity of performing experiments to identify material parameters for any degree of cure, models were developed for a spatial description of epoxy material parameters obtained at the end of the process, assuming a dependency of those with the degree of cure. In this framework, this study presents the effects of epoxy plasticity modelling for internal stress and damage prediction induced by the curing process of a thick matrix. As a first approach, a simple cut-off fracture model based on the maximal tensile stress is used to identify the weakest parts of the solid matrix. The material behavior of the matrix is first described by a perfect elasto-plastic and hydrodynamic constitutive law. In a second step, a Ramberg-Osgood model was used to improve the description of the epoxy plasticity. Identifications of damage area within thick epoxy samples after a laser induced shock wave are performed to assess simulation results for damage prediction.

1 INTRODUCTION

High performance epoxies are more and more used for structural applications, namely for naval and offshore structures as well as for aeronautical and aerospace structures. It is well known today that internal residual stresses are developed during the curing of thermosetting materials. However, several defects like cracks and bubbles inside of the matter might arise, especially with increasing thickness. These defects may provoke serious damages within the structure in service, especially under dynamic solicitations. In order to offer a better quality control, pulsed lasers have recently been used in non destructive inspection and characterization of composites [2]. This work focuses on internal gradients of properties generated during the curing and their consequences on the dynamical behavior of the LY 556® epoxy. Couplings induced by the curing between the chemistry, the thermal and the mechanics of the matrix in progress are presented and are taken into account for a spatial description within the matrix. This paper presents therefore simulation results for a coin shaped cylinder of 32 mm of diameter and 1 mm of thickness, exposed to laser induced shock waves, by taken into account radial

gradients of properties induced by the curing. The loading chosen is a realistic pressure pulse resulting from a laser-matter interaction in water confined geometry, corresponding to a 600MPa loading with an approximative duration of 10 ns. A first numerical model evidences the evolution of the time of arrival of the wave along a radius, from the loaded face to the free surface, for two mechanical behaviours: Perfect Elasto-Plastic and Rambert-Osgood models. A second numerical modeling predicts, by the use of a simple damage model (cut-off), the possible location of the crack.

2 THICK EPOXY CURING

The resin system tested in this study is a three-component anhydride-epoxy system from Ciba. The blend consists of a bifunctional DGEBA-type epoxy (Araldite LY556, EEW=183-192 g/eq, $n=0.3$), a tetra-fonctionnal anhydride hardener (methyl-tetrahydrophthalic anhydride HY 917, anhydride equivalent weight = 166g/eq), and an accelerator (1-methyl imidazole DY 070). The components were mixed in LY 556/HY 917/DY 070 weight ratio of 100/90/1, resulting in a stoichiometric epoxy-anhydride mixture.

2.1 Observations

To illustrate the challenge of the curing for thick epoxies, curing of a 32 mm diameter cylindrical block with a high of 30 mm was performed. Two cure schedules done in a 6 mm thick steel cylinder were performed and results are exposed in Fig. 1

Figure 1. LY556 epoxy resin blocs cured at 120 °C (left) and 80°C (right) during 2 hours, heating ramp 3°C/min.

These pictures clearly demonstrates cracks and defects for the 120°C curing plateau, denoting bad cure schedule process related to overheating of the matter due to the thermal and chemical coupling during the curing [1].

2.2 Cure kinetics

As the curing evolves, the chemical degree of conversion rate is less and less important and the thermosetting reaction becomes diffusion controlled [3]. Thus, a semi-empirical relationship (1) proposed by Fournier et al. and based on free volume consideration, was chosen for the description of diffusion effects. Fournier et al. extended the Kamal and Sourour model by a diffusion factor $fd(\alpha)$ as presented by equation (1):

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2 \alpha^m)(1-\alpha)^n f_d(\alpha); \quad (1)$$

$$f_d(\alpha) = \left[\frac{2}{(1+\exp[(\alpha-\alpha_f)/b])} - 1 \right]; K_1 = A_1 \exp\left(\frac{-E_1}{RT}\right); K_2 = A_2 \exp\left(\frac{-E_2}{RT}\right)$$

α_f is the degree of conversion measured at the end of a given isothermal curing and b is an empiric diffusion constant of the material. The methodology for cure kinetics identification with diffusion effects was detailed in [4].

2.3 Thermal, chemical and mechanical coupling during the curing

The local temperature T of the matrix during the curing is defined by following equation of heat transfer:

$$\rho C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = -\text{div}\{\lambda_T [-\text{grad} T]\} + r + \rho \Delta H^r \frac{d\alpha}{dt} - T \{(3\lambda + 2\mu) \alpha_T\} \text{tr} \underline{\underline{\epsilon}}^e \quad (2)$$

where C_p , λ_T , ρ and r stand respectively for specific heat, thermal conductivity, density and heat radiation imposed by the oven. α_T is the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the matrix in formation. λ and μ are the Lamé coefficients of the matrix. Nevertheless, with increasing thickness, mass effect of the epoxy has to be taken into account because of the exothermal aspect of the thermosetting reaction. This statement is clearly demonstrated by equation of heat transfer (2) where the coupling between the thermal and the chemistry appears.

Precise details of the numerical solving strategy were presented by the author in a previous work [1].

3 EPOXY PARAMETERS PREDICTION

3.1 Degree of cure

The FEM solving technique led to the prediction of gradients of temperature developed within the epoxy during the curing, hence gradients of degree of conversion, which are significant as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Degree of cure gradients prediction throughout the curing and compared after the process to a cross cutting of the epoxy bloc (2 hours curing plateau at 80°C).

A gradient of colour is observed, in a same manner as for degree of conversion prediction. As colour indicates different thermal history and as thermal is leading the chemistry, gradients of conversion predicted are in a reasonable shape compared to the observation of epoxy matrix.

3.2 Mechanical properties after the curing

It is assumed here that the thermal and chemical coupling problem is the main leading coupling to take into account [1]. Consequently, heat generated by the strain rate, as mentioned in equation of heat transfer (2), was considered as a second order effect. This assumption was validated by the solving of the thermal and chemical coupling only, presented in equation (2), which fits well internal temperature history prediction [1] and degree of conversion as shown in Fig. 2. Consequently, all mechanical parameters like Young modulus, bulk modulus, shear modulus, yield stress, failure stress could be considered as being dependent of degree of cure reached at return at room temperature, after the curing.

Elastic modulus E was deduced from shear modulus and Poisson ratio of the cured matrix that is supposed to be locally isotropic and homogeneous. Shear tests were performed on pure epoxy matrix samples as shown in Fig. 3. A video controlled shear technique was used and led to the plot of local shear stress versus local strain. Video controlled shear tests were performed at room temperature. Results are shown in Fig. 4. It is pointed out that elastic shear modulus was found to be around 1GPa. in the glassy state at room temperature. Thus, for a fully cured epoxy (~95% of degree of cure), shear modulus evolution versus shear strain is exposed in Fig. 4.

Figure 3. Shear test device. The white spot was used for video-control of local strain evolution.

Figure 4. Epoxy matrix local shear stress-strain curve at room temperature.

The nonlinear behavior of the matrix at room temperature could be described by a Ramberg-Osgood model such as $\tau=A+B.\gamma^n$. Mechanical parameters are summarized in table 1.

Engineering constant		Identification
Shear modulus	[MPa]	900
Yield shear stress	[MPa]	15
Yield strain	–	0.0165
Failure stress	[MPa]	45.8
Failure strain	–	0.072
A		2,47E-14
B		361,01

n	0.76
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Table 1: This is the example of a table.

4 NON-DESTRUCTIVE CHARACTERIZATION BY PULSED LASER

The non-destructive inspection of composites under laser ultrasonics or laser induced shock waves is becoming a matter of interest [2], [5]. Thick composites are preferred to be used for structures operating under severe loads. Previous studies have showed that it is possible to assess the degree of cure in a thick epoxy after cooling, by laser induced shock wave as a non-destructive technique [6].

Recently the damage of epoxy under intense laser induced shock waves has been prospected by Ecault and its behavior under shock was given by Boettger et al [7].

In all the published works, none of them considered the effect of pre-existing stresses due to the heterogeneity induced by the evolution of the degree of cure. Indeed, it has been shown in paragraph 3 that the degree of cure, in thick composites, affects mechanical characteristics like Young modulus, density, yield limit, Poisson ratio, ...

In this paragraph, a finite element model is showing the effects of the degree of cure on the time of arrival of weak laser induced shock wave at the free surface of a sample.

4.1 The laser induced shock wave

The mechanical loading induced by a high energy pulsed laser irradiation is a consequence of the laser-matter interaction. When the material receives a consequent energy in a very short time, a thin layer of it is sublimated. The expansion of the gaseous products, called plasma, creates a throttle and induces a compressive wave that will propagate in the sample. The plasma expansion can be confined by a transparent medium heavier than air, like water or glass. The resulting peak pressure and duration time are increased by 3 to 5 and an analytical relation gives the maximum pressure versus the incident density of power [8]. In the following study, the laser induced pressure in water confinement geometry is given on Fig. 5. The maximum pressure is of 600 MPa and the full width at half maximum is 10 ns. The irradiated surface was a disk of 3 mm of diameter.

4.2 Influence of the mechanical model on the free surface velocity

The free surface velocity remains the most accessible experimental parameter by using the laser Doppler interferometry that allows time resolved records. A numerical simulation of the experiments can predict this free surface velocity records as long as the mechanical behaviour of the material is known. Two mechanical models have been considered: the Perfect Elasto-Plastic Model (PEP) and the Rambert-Osgood model (RO), more realistic, described in paragraph 3.2. The hydrodynamic pressure under shock is given by $P = \sum a_i \mu^i$ where $\mu = 1 - \rho/\rho_0$ and $i \leq 3$ and a_i are material coefficients computed with the Hugoniot of the material (i.e. the possible thermomechanical states described by conservation equations of Rankine Hugoniot (3)). The thermomechanical state out of shock – i.e. in rarefaction - is given by the Mie-Grüneisen equation of state (4) [9].

$$P - P_{ref} = \frac{\Gamma_0}{\rho_0} (e - e_{ref}) \quad (3)$$

$$D = C_0 + s(u - u_0) \quad (4)$$

Figure 5. Laser induced shock wave inspection. Shock is generated along a radial path and free surface velocity is recorded in vis-à-vis.

Numerical simulations, performed with the explicit finite element code RADIOSS®, point out differences of cured epoxy behavior between chosen abscissa along a radius R. The material characteristic varies with the degree of cure along the radius. An axisymmetric model, split into 500 elements was used. The spot size sensitivity was discussed in the previous work [6]. The effect of the mechanical behavior of the material on the free surface velocity is given on Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Free surface velocity simulation for a 600 MPa laser pulse at the centre of the sample (fully cured). Thick line: Rambert-Osgood model, thin line: Perfect Elasto-Plastic model.

In the PEP model, the peak velocity (thin line) is almost flattened to its Hugoniot Elastic Limit (HEL). This is attributed to the effect of the elastic decay occurring behind the compressive wave in such short pulse. The elastic releases are faster than the shock front since they propagate in a moving media animated by the shock. Releases catch up the shock front and diminish it. The free surface velocity obtained with the RO model does not show any HEL since there is not singular point in the Hugoniot of the material in the (P,v) plane. The velocity rise is continuous and there is almost no elastic decay, this also explains why the peak velocity is higher than the one obtained with the PEP model.

4.3 Influence of degree of cure on time of flight

The degree of cure after cooling was estimated using the predictive model presented in paragraphs 2 and 3. It has been assumed a discrete the variation of mechanical properties along the radius of the coin shape sample (fig. 5). Free surface velocities for both models have been computed at several radii, for R=0;2;4;6;8;10;12;14 and 16 mm from the centre. The time of flight has been defined as being the time of arrival of the compressive wave at the free surface (peak velocity). They have been noted for each radius and model and plotted on Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Evolution of the time of flight along the sample radius for perfect elasto-plastic model (triangles) and Rambert-Osgood model (squares), for 1 mm thick sample and 600 MPa laser induced peak pressure.

Both models are sensitive to the degree of cure and give almost the same results. The time of arrival computed with the PEP model is a bit longer: as the compressive wave is diminished by the elastic decay, it is slow downed.

4.4 Effect of the cure on the damage.

A simple cut-off model has been added in the material description. In this model, elements in which pressure exceeds a pressure threshold are deleted. The pressure threshold for each degree of cure (at each radius) has been calculated as shown in paragraph 3.2.

For the PEP model, no damage was obtained because the elastic decay decreases the compressive wave and the consecutive tensile stress. For the RO model, no damage was obtained at the centre of the sample and even up to R=10 mm.

Figure 8. Numercial simulation by explicit finite elements methods with Radioss®, of pressure field during shock propagation in cured epoxy with damage model. Red is compression and blue for tensile.

A slight damage appeared at $R=12$ mm, corresponding to a degree of cure lower than 0.84 and increased for greater R (degree of cure < 0.84). Fig. 8 shows the maximum damage obtained for the lowest degree of cure at $R=16$ mm.

5 CONCLUSIONS

These preliminary calculations have showed that the degree of cure has a strong incidence on mechanical characteristics of thick epoxy material. The gradient of characteristic has been predicting by a thermomechanical coupling problem on a thick sample. Mechanical characteristics could have been evaluated in the entire sample. A slice of the sample has been subjected to laser induced shock inspection with a table top laser source. A realistic mechanical model, Rambert-Osgood, has been implemented in a finite element commercial code and showed that, by considering the time of flight at the free surface velocity, which is actually experimentally possible, it is possible to evidence the gradient of mechanical properties due to the evolution of the degree of cure. These numerical results are encouraging for performing experimental campaigns. It will be a next step of interest. Moreover, by introducing a damage model according to the degree of cure and by fixing a given pressure load, it is possible, by inspecting a radius, to find the damage threshold of the sample. The position at which damage occurs is related to the degree of cure. It is then possible to change the pressure load and run another radius for determining another damage threshold. By this way, one can obtain a relation between degree of cure and failure stress.

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